

CALL: H2020-IBA-SWAFS-SUPPORT-1-2020

TOPIC: IBA-SWAFS-SUPPORT-1-2020

SUPPORT FOR THE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION DIMENSION OF EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES (PART I)

PROJECT: Planning the Future of Research & Innovation in the European University Alliance UNITE! (UNITE.H2020)

Link to the website: <https://www.unite-university.eu/>

SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

In this policy brief, the European Universities pilot Alliances report on the progress made through cooperation in selected R&I areas and provide a first set of recommendations to the European Commission for further policy development.

Policy background:

In order to strengthen strategic partnerships across the EU amongst higher education institutions, the European Commission targets the emergence of “European Universities” by 2024 by funding alliances from across Europe. The ambitious mandate aims to trigger systemic, structural and sustainable institutionalized cooperation between higher education institutions. As a complement to the Erasmus+ action geared towards supporting higher education cooperation models, Horizon 2020 support is dedicated to contributing to the research and innovation dimension of the alliances between European universities, in line with their shared, integrated, long-term joint strategy and in synergy with their education dimension.

This initiative is one of the flagships of the [European strategy for universities](#) that aims at supporting and enabling universities to adapt to changing conditions, to thrive and to take a leading role in the recovery of Europe, and in making our society greener, more inclusive and more digital. The adoption of this strategy was accompanied by a Commission [proposal for a Council recommendation on building bridges](#) for effective European higher education cooperation.

In parallel, the [European Research Area Policy Agenda](#) sets out 20 voluntary actions for the period 2022-2024, including several of which are relevant for universities.

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS (MAX 1.5P)

1. Please describe the **challenges** your Alliance encountered regarding cooperation between universities in the field of R&I in relation to the institutional change areas (transformation modules) foreseen.

UNITE.H2020, aiming at developing the R&I dimension of the Unite! European University Alliance, enhances collaboration among the partners' universities in different R&I institutional change areas: research infrastructures - RIs (WP3), academia-business (WP4), human capital (WP5), open science (WP6), societal outreach (WP7), collaboration with other alliances (WP8).

In the first half of the project, each WP carried out an analysis of the state-of-the-art of the R&I dimension in the Unite! universities to **identify challenges and convergences**. As a result a common R&I Agenda (WP2) defining strategies and joint pilot actions will be implemented in the second half of the project.

The main challenges encountered by the consortium in the different R&I transformation modules can be summarized as follows:

- **Common framework vs different rules/ level of advancement/ institutional approach.** The analysis of the state-of-the-art carried out in this first phase of the project highlighted that there is no homogeneity at country and at university level among the partners regarding national laws and priorities, universities internal rules and strategic plans as well as a different level of advancement in the R&I institutional areas mentioned above. The challenge is to identify common frameworks for the partners' universities to start joint collaborations despite these diversities.
- **Collaboration vs competition.** The aim of the project is to find a convergence of the long-term vision of each partner for a joint R&I strategy of the Alliance, where the partners' strengths can complement each other towards a "whole beyond its parts". This is a long process, that we are initiating with UNITE.H2020. The challenge is to overcome the initial resistance of each university in making available information and know how and to demonstrate to the whole university community that collaboration in R&I creates synergies that are beneficial for all the Alliance as a whole and not only for some of the partners.
- **Activities at project level vs involvement of the university/regional ecosystem.** The initial stage of the project, the R&I collaboration of Unite! involved staff directly working in UNITE.H2020. For the effective creation and future growing of the Unite! R&I community, the challenge is the definition, creation and communication of the Unite! added value in R&I for the partners' Universities' community at all level (i.e. institutional, researchers, administrative staff, students) as well as to the Unite! regional ecosystem (industry, society etc.).
- **Lot of effort vs limited budget.** A common challenge for the UNITE.H2020 partners is the big effort required for the implementation of the project activities for the creation of the R&I dimension of the Unite! alliance compared to the available budget. Moreover, at the moment there is no certainty about future funds for the long-term sustainability of R&I strategies after the end of the project (December 2023).

2. Please describe how you tackled or intend to **tackle these challenges**. Based on your project's experience so far (and if applicable), briefly outline case(s) that you consider as **good practice** and of interest to other universities or to policy-makers.

Depending on their specific topic, WPs have been tackling the above-mentioned challenges.

- In order to identify rules and approaches, overcome barriers and finally define **common frameworks**, each WP carried out an analysis of the state-of-the-art of the universities in the different institutional areas. All the WPs made extensive use of surveys, interview as well as desk research as instruments for the collection of data and information. The analysis of these data led to the identification of common traits and best practices and a possible definition of common frameworks among partners. An example of methodology used at this scope was the use of SWOT analysis and gap analysis (e.g. WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6). In this phase, the partners had the opportunity to get to know each other, their differences and similarities, and above all finding a common "language", thus laying the basis to understand each other and collaborate. WP3, for example, initially worked to find a common and shared definition of "Research Infrastructure".
- In order to promote **collaboration among the partner** and the **involvement of the university/regional ecosystem** some actions were undertaken: taking advantage of the increasing use of web meetings the WPs met often that initially foreseen, thus facilitating relationship, best practices

exchange and community building. Staff not initially working for the UNITE.H2020 project has been also involved as the already existing collaborations and initiatives among partners were considered as best practices for the pilot planning. This happened for example, in WP3 for the research collaborations with sharing of RIs and WP4 for the project/collaborations with Unite! partners and companies to test the new model of collaboration based in Unite! The use of already known initiatives at the partners' universities was also the strategy used by WP7 for the involvement and outreach of the society (e.g. Researchers' Night). Also WP8 based on existing collaborative contacts to partners of other Alliances to select Alliances for potential collaboration with Unite!

- **Lot of effort vs limited budget:** considering the wide institutional changes foreseen in the project there is the need to ensure long-term sustainability of the actions with additional funding. Therefore as stated in the position paper on Joint statement of all 41 European University Alliances on the need for long-term sustainable funding that allows Alliances to work across all their missions, Unite! welcome the European Commission initiatives to continue supporting the European University's research missions, as research is central to the work of universities.
3. Please describe the **tangible progress** that individual partners as well as the Alliance as a whole have made in terms of introducing changes in their entities as a result of this project. Please elaborate on whether the inclusive and integrated cooperation approach of your alliance helps accelerate institutional change of all partners (e.g. through sharing of practices from institutions with strong expertise or infrastructure in specific areas to institutions without).

After the analysis of the state of the art and the identification of best practices several pilots have been defined to help accelerate institutional change of all partners, thus laying the basis for future actions after the project end. The tangible progress of the Alliance as a whole are summarized below:

- WP2: common R&I Agenda with an action plan consisting of several pilots, thus laying the basis for a long term institutional changes
- WP3: common guidelines for research infrastructure sharing.
- WP4: creation of a network of TTOs and definition of a common the value proposition
- WP5: research career framework guidelines
- WP6: open science and innovation strategic roadmap with recommendations for university leaders and regional and national policymakers for advancing the adoption of open science practices
- WP7: first joint Unite! Researchers' Night 2021 on "Energy" organized in September 2021, with the participation of 5 researchers presenting their research topics to 6 school classes from 4 different countries
- WP8: networking with other European Alliance for sharing best practices and enhance collaboration with the Unite!EUAlliance
- WP9: communication& dissemination plan in order to foster the community building

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS (MAX 3P)

In this section, the European Universities pilot Alliances make recommendations in relation to the following policy topics.

1. Policy topic 1: facilitating transnational cooperation

Knowing that the Commission proposed a [Council recommendation to facilitate transnational collaboration between universities](#), which action should be prioritised to address the challenges you encountered as an Alliance in sharing capacities, infrastructures, resources or staff in R&I?

Considering the priorities of the Unite! European University Alliance, according to the Council recommendations actions to be prioritized are:

Sustainable long-term funding for the existing Alliance will ensure a deep transformation in institutional change areas: in particular seed funding for developing structures and infrastructures to support joint research and innovation.

Seed funding for research activity (also in collaboration with industry) and the mobility of researchers and PhD students to stimulate R&I collaboration between partners and also with their ecosystem, contributing to the creation of the alliance R&I community.

The establishment of a joint European degree covering all levels (Bachelor, Master, Doctorate and lifelong learning opportunities) should be developed as a clear quality certificate with accompanied calls/funding. This includes **Doctorate opportunities**. The PhD, as both last step of education and possible first step of a researcher career, is the natural link between the educational and R&I dimension of all alliances. An holistic, integrated, programmatic support of the alliances, providing long-term sustainable funding of PhD positions to the universities partners of an alliance, under the condition that they are used for the development of R&I projects of joint interest for different alliance partners, is a comparatively easy win and could have a strong impact on developing a common R&I agenda; strengthening the collaboration in R&I among the alliance partners; sharing research infrastructures; developing joint strategies, criteria and approaches to the management of researcher careers; etc..

2. Policy topic 2: strengthening careers

Is there a need to develop a model tenure-track system at European level to contribute to solving precariousness of early career researchers? If you believe so, how do you think it should be structured?

Each institution has its assessment (recruitment and promotion) systems. Some countries have national rules and national agencies of accreditation.

The development of **general guidelines for assessment** is important, allowing all the institutions to follow a common framework. This would allow the institutions to adjust and optimize their internal systems, enabling a better alignment and harmonisation among each other.

In some countries/institutions, a pure research career is almost inexistent, and for all the institutions the majority of their academics have as core activities both research and teaching. This reality gives awareness to the need for specific investment. Thus, the **general framework for universities funding for this strategic policy must be also considered** to enable successful implementation.

In light of the [policy process on the reform of assessment](#) of research and institutions, what are your recommendations on how to address academic/researcher career assessment?

The scoping report of the European Commission "Towards a reform of the research assessment system" highlights the need to acquire means of evaluating the quality of research activities based on indicators other than the bibliometric ones usually used. This leads to two questions:

- What **quality attributes** are wish to assess precisely?
- How to get a **fair evaluation** of these attributes?

The answer to the first question is provided in the "scoping report" as well as in other documents¹ in general, but this answer does not include the means of evaluating these attributes. It therefore seems useful to work in parallel on the two questions:

It is indeed difficult to assess quality attributes that are not quantifiable. It can even be dangerous because it could introduce additional biases to the evaluation process.

Within the project, we took as a working basis the "RH framework" of UCL (University College London)² which has the merit of defining a graduated method of evaluation, a method which today seems to be absent from most universities in the countries participating in the project. Although it does not precisely define the means of evaluating each attribute, it proposes a 4-level scale to assess the merit of a professional in each field of activity (teaching, research, external relations, collective activities) as well as criteria to assess each level. This is particularly interesting for the evaluation of research activities.

Our recommendation for longer-term work is:

- To define a **generic framework** that can be adapted to the specificities of each discipline and, possibly, each country, **with precise quality criteria to be assessed** and which should allow an overall assessment of the level reached by a researcher (the number of levels could be equal to 4, as in the UCL framework, or lower).
- To define, for each quality criterion, **precise means of evaluating or certifying them**.

3. Policy topic 3: digital transition

What are the specific needs of the Alliances to accelerate their digital transition in the R&I dimension, and how can this be addressed at the EU level?

In particular, do you see a need for additional dedicated e-infrastructures for data storage and management that are distributed and interoperable? Please take into account progress regarding the development of the federated e-infrastructure for research outputs (EOSC, see [ERA Policy Agenda](#)), and the implementation of a digital platform for cooperation in higher education (see the [European strategy for universities](#)).

University alliances necessitate information interchange among all universities in order to fulfil the alliance's goals, such as a joint European degree, as well as information exchange with other organisations in order to participate in European projects connected to digital transition. To that purpose, **the more uniformity there is, the smoother the digital transformation**.

Our universities are committed to provide as many high-quality mobility opportunities to our students and staff as possible – both within and outside the European Union – while transitioning to a fully digital approach as key players in Europe's digital transition.

At the moment, universities across Europe are working at varying paces to implement European initiatives such as EWP and the European Student Card, often with strict deadlines. This places institutions across the EU in difficult situations that, if not resolved, may result in less mobility opportunities for our students and staff in the future. Higher Education Institutions, therefore, **require the needed assistance, time, and flexibility** to provide truly exceptional mobility experiences and to reduce the administrative burden.

To that aim, **digital platforms** for collaboration, or a **marketplace** of accelerated services, to support interactions, as well as the usage of **federated e-infrastructure for research outputs** would represent an added value. These digital e-infrastructure should ensure open as possible –ethical and legal– and permanent open scientific knowledge access – data, code, methods, prototypes, results – for everyone. This infrastructure should allow interoperability, guarantee implementing FAIR data principles, and ensure safety and security.

4. Policy topic 4: access to excellence

¹ <https://www.uu.nl/sites/default/files/UU-Recognition-and-Rewards-Vision.pdf>, sfdora.org, <https://open-science-training-handbook.gitbook.io/book/open-science-basics/open-concepts-and-principles>, <https://www.vsnul.nl/recognitionandrewards/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Position-paper-Room-for-everyone%E2%80%99s-talent.pdf>

² https://www.ucl.ac.uk/human-resources/sites/human_resources/files/academic_careers_framework.pdf

What is your advice on how to accelerate access to excellence in science and in value creation for all participants for higher education institutions across the entire ERA, through the European Universities Initiative?

Different institutions within the alliance exhibit a demonstrated excellence profile in different areas. A well-established, long-term network could provide the basis for fostering access to this excellence. A balanced mechanism for supporting researchers and institutions access to the institutions and laboratories where this excellence resides could be key to fostering excellence overall.

5. Policy topic 5: increasing global competitiveness

Europe's relative weight at a global level when it comes to research-intensive universities is shrinking. In light of this, a European Excellence Initiative will be established to improve global competitiveness of Europe's universities, in synergy with the European Universities Initiative of Erasmus+. In your view, what would be key elements of such an Initiative? Secondly, could you envisage that such an initiative specifically targets EU objectives such as the Green Deal or European Missions?

The European University funding must integrate all university's missions (education, research, innovation, transfer to society) and (2) combine resources (Erasmus+ , Digital Europe, Interregional Innovation Investments, member state funding, etc.) reflecting not only the knowledge square approach, but also the infrastructural and other supports needed to drive the development of globally competitive European University Alliances. This is the main necessity that the alliance can drive a globally competitive European Education and Research Area.

6. Other recommendations

European University Alliances should also foster entrepreneurship in two main directions: i) fostering start-up and spin-off initiatives in Universities; ii) creating improved synergies with investors, accelerators, incubators and corporate entrepreneurship, because of the EU dimension of the networks.

Fostering good practices in Open Science and Innovation will ensure value creation for all participants for HEI across the entire ERA, contributing to sharing and reusing data, enhancing transparency and accountability, contributing to a more democratic access to knowledge. This would ensure the involvement of all countries (leave no one behind): to solve global challenges the needs of all players should be considered. Actions could be targeted at achieving the following objectives (highlighted in D.6.1 of UNITE.H2020 project):

- Developing open science policies and open science strategies at European University Alliance level, in order to boost a culture of openness across their research communities
- Enhancing the opening up of physical infrastructures (other than digital ones, above mentioned)
- Promoting open science support services, by developing university level open science units for supporting their researcher communities along the different stages of the open scientific process.
- Fostering open science in careers, by reviewing regional and national research career evaluation systems to align them with the adoption of open science principles, practices and goals
- Improving open science competencies such as promote multilingual open educational resources on open science for the capacity- building of their research communities training in open science infrastructure, tools and skills for everyone.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No [101017408-UNITE.H2020]

This policy brief reflects only the author's view and the European Commission/REA is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.